

Efficiency Lane: Task-Specific Adapters against Fine-tuning RoBERTa

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Abstract

We evaluate adapters as a parameter efficient alternative to conventional fine-tuning methods for adapting a pre-trained model to out-of-domain tasks. We take a base model RoBERTa and second-phase pre-trained variations of it, and employ a dual approach: i) fine-tune the base model to perform a specific task, and ii) train adapter modules for the same task. We observe that adapters can achieve comparable performance to fine-tuning. A similar observation can be made even when the model undergoes a second-phase of task-adaptive pre-training before fine-tuning. Beyond comparable performance, adapters have significant benefits over fine-tuning, in terms of greatly reduced trainable parameters, ability to perform sequential training on tasks, and combining multiple adapters to create a single model capable of performing multiple tasks.

1. Introduction/Background/Motivation

1.1. Objective

We explore how traditional methods using fine-tuning compare to newer architectures using adapters in the context of transfer learning with pre-trained models for natural language tasks. We conduct a comparison across 4 types of pre-trained models that have been used before in other studies [5]. 1. A generic LLM, RoBERTa. 2. An LLM pre-trained on text in the domain of a task (DAPT). 3. An LLM pre-trained on the unlabeled data from a specific task (TAPT) 4. LLM pre-trained on both (DAPT + TAPT).

Adapters are more lightweight, modular and composable than traditional fine-tuning methods. However, there may exist a performance penalty due to the reduced number of trainable parameters. This project looks at using parameter-efficient adapters for the RoBERTa transformer to achieve comparable performance to fine-tuning. Expanding from (Houlsby et al., 2019), our scope consists of two adapter configurations (Pfeiffer and Houlsby) imposed over tasks that contain specialized language and domains not extensively available in the base RoBERTa model. This allows us to assess if adapters can infuse knowledge efficiently, in a way that is comparable to Gururangan’s Task Adap-

tive Pretraining (TAPT) with small datasets related to two tasks in the Computer Science domain and one task for Biomedicine. Additionally, we evaluate the effectiveness of Adapter Fusion, a recently proposed multi-task learning architecture that aims to leverage multiple modular adapters using an attention layer.

Throughout the study, we evaluate our models and compare them by the F1-Macro Score and the number of trainable parameters of their network, with specific focus on traditional fine-tuning, TAPT pre-training, and adapter methods. Albeit we focus on a small number of low-resource tasks (< 5K records), the results support the potential of adapters as a parameter-efficient contestant to fine-tuning and as a viable alternative to TAPT for some use-cases, such as mid-sized (> 3K) datasets.

1.2. Current State

A common practice today is to start with a model pre-trained on a broad corpus of information (such as books, websites and other general domains) and then use fine-tuning to train the model for a particular task. If the task sits within a specific domain not originally covered by model, continued pre-training can be done on specific unlabelled corpus. Once a baseline pre-trained model has been established, task specific heads are added as the final layers, which get co-trained with the baseline weights using task specific labeled data. Fine-tuning has been shown to be very effective at performing a given task.

- **Pre-Trained Models** like RoBERTa, a bidirectional encoder model, uses techniques like Masked Language Modeling (MLM) and Next Sentence Prediction (NSP) to learn a deep understanding of language structure and continuity. An optional second phase of pre-training [5] continues the process on new data using the same unsupervised learning objectives. The internal weights and embeddings of the model are shifted to better represent the vocabulary and patterns found in the new data. These processes are often quite demanding in terms of data and compute resources.
- **Full Fine-Tuning** is then used retrain the entire model on the task data. While this would likely lead to the

Model	Parameter Counts	Parameters Trained	Percentage Trained
RoBERTa and full fine-tuning	124,650,246	124,650,246	100.00%
Pfeiffer Adapters	126,777,759	2,127,513	1.71%
Houlsby Adapters	127,672,287	3,022,041	2.42%

Table 1. **Model Parameters and Training Percentage for Pre-Training, Fine-Tuning and Adapters**

best performance, studies have shown that earlier layers of the pre-trained model generally learn broad semantic and syntactic features and those don’t really change for any given task. Limitations of fine-tuning include the need to store and share a complete set of weights for each task, and the requirement to train all tasks simultaneously to avoid catastrophic forgetting [8].

- **Variable Fine-Tuning** arises as a more efficient way to fine-tune. Researchers have shown that Parameter-Efficient-Fine-Tuning (PEFT) methods that focus only on a small proportion of model weights (original or new), while keeping the remaining weights frozen, can match the performance of traditional full fine-tuning methods [6] and address some of their limitations, largely as they preserve much of the original knowledge while still adapting to new tasks. Some examples of PEFT methods include adapters, which are small neural modules that are added to the pre-trained model and trained only on the task data.

1.3. Motivation

Fine-tuning has several benefits as it allows to use the learned representations of large pre-trained models for specific tasks. However, it also has some drawbacks:

- Fine-tuning involves training a large number of parameters for each task. For large models which can be 100s of MB, storing and sharing a complete set of weights for each task can limit multi-task applications.
- All tasks must be trained simultaneously, limiting scalability. Sequential fine-tuning for multiple tasks leads to catastrophic forgetting [8]

Adapters do not suffer from these drawbacks [6]. The number of trained parameters is a tiny fraction compared to fine-tuning, significantly reducing the computational resources for fine-tuning as shown in Table 1. This is achieved through the use of bottleneck architecture, which involves downsizing the outputs of the previous layer, passing them through a non-linearity, and then upsizing them to match the inputs of the next layer. Additionally, adapters are modular as multiple adapters can be loaded onto the same base model to perform multiple tasks, eliminating the need for a copy of the base model for each task. Further, as they preserve the original model weights, they are more capable

of maintaining the base model integrity and performance across tasks.

Adapter Fusion is an extension of the adapter architecture [9]. In Adapter Fusion, several trained adapters are combined in parallel, and an attention layer is added on top of the adapters to combine (fuse) them. Adapter fusion is then retrained on one of the original adapter’s tasks while updating the fusion layer and the classification head. We are interested in finding if this approach leads to better performance than a stand-alone adapter. Fusion allows the new model to leverage the original adapters information plus the potentially beneficial information from the other adapters without modifying their weights. This can lead to performance beyond just the original adapter while only minimally increasing the number of parameters. Additionally, by locking the base model and the adapter parameters the fusion setup avoids the problem of catastrophic forgetting that is typically an issue when fine tuning for multi-task training.

Gururangan et al. [5] highlights the benefits of domain-adaptive pre-training (DAPT) and task-adaptive pre-training (TAPT), which tailor the pre-training phase to more closely align with the characteristics of the target tasks, potentially enhancing subsequent fine-tuning outcomes. For instance, they expose low vocabulary overlap between RoBERTa and the domain of Computer Science, and find that continued pre-training on this domain is beneficial for related tasks. Their insights are crucial for informing more efficient strategies for effective task-specific tuning, although they rely on expensive methods of retraining and fine-tuning. In “Parameter-Efficient Transfer Learning for NLP” [6], the authors show that adapters attain within 0.4% of the performance of full-fine-tuning, adding only 3.6% parameters per task. The paper used the BERT transformer as its pre-trained model and used tasks from the GLUE benchmark to prove its assertions.

We study parameter-efficient task adaptation using the RoBERTa model, which is a more robust version of BERT [7], and compare the results to those of Gururangan et al. [5]. As per Houlsby et al. [6], we expect the performance of adapters to be comparable to full fine-tuning, and further explore the capabilities for adapters as a viable alternative to TAPT to perform on out-of-domain tasks.

Domain	Task	Label Type	Train	Dev	Test	Classes
Computer Science	ACL-ARC	citation intent	1,688	114	139	6
	SCIERC	relation classification	3,219	455	974	7
BIOMED	CHEMPROT	relation classification	4,169	2,427	3,469	13

Table 2. **Dataset Statistics**

2. Approach

Our objective is to establish adapters as a suitable transfer learning approach for a given task, as compared with fine-tuning and task-adaptive pretraining methods. For this we recreate a fine-tuning the baseline that was used in the transfer learning paper [5]. We then take the four pre-trained models (RoBERTa base, DAPT, TAPT, DAPT-TAPT) per task and train adapters under two configurations, Pfeiffer and Houlsby. Our results are directly comparable to the original paper [5] and our own reproduction of their results.

2.1. Data, Domain, and Tasks

We take data available to download by Allen Institute [2]. Our scope outlined in Table 2 is a subset of tasks from Gururanga et al. [5] that includes two tasks under the CS domain, ACL-ARC (citation-intent) and SCIERC (relation classification), and one task from BIOMED domain, CHEMPROT (relation classification) to test our hypothesis under a new domain. All these tasks have under 5,000 training records (i.e., low-resource)¹.

The task datasets have similar class distribution and are imbalanced, as shown in Figure B.4. Therefore, we use the F1 score as our evaluation metric², which is a better measure for imbalanced datasets. The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, and is a better measure for imbalanced datasets. Also, this is the same metric used in the original paper [5] so it allows for comparison of results.

2.2. Methodology

Base Models and Fine-Tuning For reproduction, we first aimed to use the same set-up as in Gururanga et al. [2] but encountered limitations on compatibility with newer packages and versioning. Therefore, we chose the widely used HuggingFace Transformers library [4] for training our models. We load the pre-trained models from [2] made publicly available C.6, and fine-tune by training a classification head in supervised manner using the same task-specific datasets and similar approach to Gururangan et. al. [5]. We

¹Attempts were made to train on high-resource tasks, but due to computational demands, this was infeasible within our timeframe and is set as a future objective. We further exclude the low-resource NEWS task HYPERPARTISIAN as the test/validation dataset is very small and has only 2 classes - this leads to inconsistent results from [2] under our current set-up, again to be investigated as a future objective.

²Following [5], we use macro-f1 for our CS tasks and micro-f1 for the CHEMPROT task

were able to recreate results that are close-enough to the reference paper (better in some cases), but further efforts may be needed for closer replication and inspection of original process³. The F1 metric from our version of fine-tuning results is taken as a benchmark to assess the performance of adapter methods.

Figure 1. Illustration: Optuna Hyperparameter Search of combinations for roberta-base SCIERC Task (Houlsby)

Adapters To assess the efficacy of adapter methods, we integrate task-specific adapters (and a prediction head) to each of the base models and train them separately using task-specific data. For training and managing configurations, we use AdapterHub [1] and two architectures:

- Pfeiffer [10] is a lightweight configuration that adds adapter modules between feed-forward layers. This minimally disrupts the base representations and maintains ability to generalize while adapting to new tasks.
- Houlsby [6] can handle more complexity as it also adds adapters within the multi-head attention layers of each block. This allows the adapters to modulate both the attention outputs and feedforward operations, potentially offering more task-specific adaptation.

The Appendix F shows examples of the adapter modules added to the model for both configurations. Note the bottleneck architecture of the adapter modules. We compare results under two scopes: direct fine-tuning comparison, and continued task-adaptive pre-training comparison.

Adapter Fusion For each task we created a fusion “within” the same domain (the adapter for that task plus an adapter for the other task in the same domain) and a fusion “cross” with another domain (the original adapter for that domain plus a task outside that domain). To evaluate the impact of additional domain pre-training we analyze adapter

³Although benchmark fine-tuning results broadly align, there are some differences, likely due to differences in infrastructure, libraries used, and possibly unreported training parameters. Biggest relative difference is our F1 roberta-base for ACL-ARC at 66.34 while Gururanga’s is 63.00

fusion for both Roberta-base as well as the CS-Roberta. We also restricted the analysis to just the Pfeiffer Adapter.

Evaluation Macro F1 Score Across Different Seeds for Each Trial
task: SCIERC, version: v01

Figure 2. Illustration: Optuna trial results show convergence to good hyperparameter choices, other tasks follow similar patterns

2.3. Hyperparameter Search and Model Training

For training our adapters, by focusing on hyperparameter efficiency and robust training techniques, we achieved competitive results against traditional fine-tuning approaches, as detailed in our results from Table 3 with configuration E.8. Our approach demonstrates that adapters, when optimized properly, can effectively leverage pre-trained models for task-specific applications, and be on-par or surpass our baseline fine-tuning strategies.

Hyperparameter Search: Optuna [3] was chosen as our hyperparameter optimization framework, especially useful in adapter training to traverse the combinations of learning rates, batch sizes and epochs. For a given search range E.9, the framework applies Tree-Structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) that allowed for quick convergence to optimal settings, as illustrated in Figure 2. Each combination runs within a trial, and each trial is composed of 5 random seeds⁴. The mean F1 on the test dataset is set as a performance metric for each trial, and we report this together with its standard deviation across the seeds. Smaller datasets often benefit from more granular updates (i.e., small batches) and moderate learning rates prevent overfitting. Our best hyperparameters reflect this, as shown in Figure 1 and Ta-

⁴The processes we ran also showed a lot of stochasticity across runs. We smoothed out most of the variance by the use of five random seeds, which helped in comparing across different runs. This is in line with [2] who report high standard deviation in their results, and also follow a 5-seed mean approach.

ble E.10. The number of training epochs does not show a clear correlation with the F1 score, as the models seem to require few iterations to capture task specifics.

Figure 3. Example of Learning Curve convergence for roberta-base SCIERC Task (Houlsby) for the 5 seeds in best trial

Training Optimization: All models were trained using the Adam optimizer with L2 regularization, which is standard within the HuggingFace Transformers library. Since our tasks were all related to classification, cross-entropy loss was used for training. We adapted the learning rate and batch size based on outcomes from the Optuna search to maximize F1 score. Our experiments show robust performance across multiple training seeds, as shown in Figure 3.

2.4. Approach Remarks

Based on recent research showing the efficacy of adapters at performing on par with fine-tuning approaches [6], we felt confident that we can get comparable results with adapters. However, we take as baseline our reproduced results for fine-tuning as in [5], which may not have been the best fine-tuning results possible for our tasks. We also note that the results of our fine-tuning are better than the original paper, which may be due to differences in infrastructure, libraries used, and possibly unreported training parameters.

Given the higher number of trainable parameters for adapters with Houlsby configuration, we expected Houlsby to have a better performance. Since we train on low-resource (small) datasets, the full benefits of the additional complexity of Houlsby may not be entirely realized in our experiments.

3. Experiments and Results

For our fine-tuning experiments, we add a classifier layer to the pre-trained models and co-train all the pre-trained weights and the classifier with the task data. For our adapters-based experiments, we add the adapters to the pre-trained models and the classification heads. We then train the adapters, which only trains the adapter layers and the final classification heads, without changing any of the pre-trained weights.

Pre-trained Model	Fine-Tuning		Adapters		Adapter Fusion	
	Gururangan	Our Baseline	Pfeiffer	Houlsby	Within	Cross
ACL-ARC						
ROBERTA	63.00 _{5.80}	66.34 _{4.67}	67.12 _{1.85}	65.53 _{1.30}	73.30 [†] _{0.38}	72.35 _{1.29}
TAPT	67.40 _{1.80}	69.49 _{2.24}	67.22 _{3.92}	65.12 _{1.22}		
DAPT	<u>75.40</u> _{2.50}	74.65 _{3.33}	73.32 _{1.79}	74.03 _{3.36}	73.59 _{0.49}	74.06 _{1.27}
DAPT_TAPT	<u>75.60</u> _{3.80}	74.89 _{2.48}	73.20 _{2.84}	72.24 _{1.55}		
SCIERC						
ROBERTA	77.30 _{1.90}	80.02 _{1.20}	81.60 _{0.42}	81.32 _{0.71}	80.32 _{0.21}	80.32 _{0.15}
TAPT	79.30 _{1.50}	80.95 _{0.74}	80.80 _{1.35}	80.92 _{0.76}		
DAPT	80.80 _{1.50}	83.08 _{1.16}	82.48 _{0.54}	82.55 _{0.81}	81.64 _{0.28}	81.53 _{0.63}
DAPT_TAPT	81.30 _{1.80}	81.55 _{0.74}	81.47 _{0.70}	88.81 _{0.58}		
CHEMPROT						
ROBERTA	<u>81.90</u> _{0.10}	80.69 _{0.55}	80.38 _{0.52}	80.95 _{0.40}		80.55 _{0.11}
TAPT	<u>82.60</u> _{0.40}	79.88 _{0.66}	80.80 _{0.45}	80.67 _{0.65}		
DAPT	<u>84.20</u> _{0.20}	81.72 _{0.41}	81.85 _{0.51}	82.16 _{0.68}		82.77 [†] _{0.29}
DAPT_TAPT	<u>84.40</u> _{0.40}	81.71 _{0.92}	81.67 _{0.39}	82.29 _{0.40}		

Table 3. **Comparison of Fine-tuning and Adapter Methods** We show baseline from the original paper [5] for reference but use our baseline for comparison with other methods. We further add results for Adapter Fusion, that is based on Pfeiffer adapters. Adapter Fusion was performed for within domain tasks (e.g., fuse ACL-ARC and SCIERC) and cross-domain tasks (e.g., fuse ACL-ARC and CHEMPROT). The best results are in bold (where [5] wins, its underlined, where Adapter Fusion wins, it is in *italics*[†]).

3.1. Results

Table 1 shows the total parameter counts of the models when using fine-tuning and the adapters. Note that the Pfeiffer configuration is much more parameter-efficient than the Houlsby configuration, as it introduces fewer layers. A sample of the layers can be found in Appendix F.

3.2. Adapters vs Fine-Tuning

Based on our empirical results in Table 3, we see that both adapter configurations, Pfeiffer and Houlsby, were able to achieve on-par performance as full fine-tuning. The Pfeiffer configuration has an average difference of -0.33% vs full fine-tuning and the Houlsby configuration shows a difference of 0.17% D.7⁵. This is in line with the results shown in other studies [6]. The results clearly demonstrate the capacity of adapters to be as effective at transfer learning as full fine-tuning. The comparison of the models in Table 1 also shows that the adapters needed just a fraction of the total parameters (1.71% for Pfeiffer and 2.42% for Houlsby) to be trained to achieve comparable results.

This is quite a significant advantage of adapters, as they allow us to achieve the same results in transfer learning as full-fine-tuning, with just a tiny fraction of the trainable parameters needed for full fine-tuning. As discussed earlier, in Section 1.3, this was one of the motivations for this study.

⁵The Houlsby results have an outlier for SciERC and dapt.tapt that performs 8.9% better than fine-tuning. Future work will investigate this outlier for confirmation of results.

3.3. Adapters vs Continued Pre-Training

Adapters serve as both a complement to traditional fine-tuning and as a standalone alternative, offering targeted task optimization while reducing computational costs, which is especially beneficial in settings with limited resources.

Base PT Model	TAPT	Adapter	
		(Base)	(TAPT)
ACL-ARC			
ROBERTA	69.49 _{2.24}	67.12 _{1.85}	67.22 _{3.92}
DAPT	74.89 _{2.48}	74.03* _{3.36}	74.03* _{3.36}
SCIERC			
ROBERTA	80.95 _{0.74}	81.60 _{0.42}	80.92* _{0.76}
DAPT	81.55 _{0.74}	82.55* _{0.81}	88.81 * _{0.58}
CHEMPROT			
ROBERTA	79.88 _{0.66} ↓	80.95 * _{0.40}	80.80 _{0.45}
DAPT	81.71 _{0.92} ↓	82.16* _{0.51}	82.29 * _{0.40}

Table 4. **Adapters as an alternative to TAPT** The best results are in bold. Note that entries in the matrix that fall for both DAPT and TAPT have three phases of pre-training (base, DAPT and TAPT). For Adapters, where it includes a * it refers to Houlsby adapters, otherwise is Pfeiffer. A down arrow ↓ in TAPT indicates its the lowest score in the row.

From Table 4 we further observe that using adapters without additional task-specific pre-training (as indicated by Adapter (Base)) provided comparable performance to using TAPT plus fine-tuning. This provides indication that, for some cases, adapters can serve as an alternative to TAPT,

possibly due to an ability to infuse task-specific knowledge into the network through the new layers. This is especially useful for low-resource tasks, where the cost of additional pre-training may not be justified. It’s possible that TAPT may not provide as much benefit over adapters in our experiments since the task-specific terms may not be well-represented in the first phase pre-training corpus. Adapters allow for more targeted adjustments to the model, focusing specifically on the task-relevant aspects of the language without requiring extensive re-training of the model.

The experiments suggest that domain-specific pre-training (DAPT) provides a strong foundation for tasks within that domain, and adapters can effectively leverage and build upon this foundation. Adapters appear to be effective across different sizes of datasets. For smaller datasets, like ACL-ARC and SCIERC, they can provide the necessary specialization without extensive re-training. For larger datasets, such as CHEMPROT, adapters actually improve performance, indicating their utility across different scales of data availability.

3.4. Pfeiffer vs Housby

Given the higher number of trainable parameters with Housby compared to Pfeiffer, we expected Housby configuration to perform better than Pfeiffer, in general. While the sample size of tasks is small to imply too broad a conclusion, we can see that for the chosen tasks and optimized training, the Housby configuration was slightly better than Pfeiffer, especially when the dataset is larger. When the datasets are small there is no discernible difference, as both configurations are equally capable of optimal learning. It is expected that Housby would be better generally, given the higher number of trained parameters introduced by the Housby configuration (2.42% vs 1.71%). However, Pfeiffer configuration does have a definite advantage of being more parameter-efficient and this would be a desirable quality when we are talking of lots of tasks. We could see a bit of tradeoff in parameter-efficient configuration vs task performance for bigger datasets.

3.5. Adapter Fusion

The “Within” adapter fusion results 3 were surprising for the ACL-ARC task. While the DAPT aligned with expectations, slightly exceeding that of the Pfeiffer adapter, the RoBERTa results far exceeded the adapter and were on par with DAPT. This could be because the training data of the SCI-ERC and was in the same domain, and so it was able to leverage some of that knowledge improve results.

The “Within” adapter fusion results for the SCI-ERC task performed slightly worse than the solo adapter. This could be for several reasons, the selection of the specific adapters 5 runs, the exact hyperparameters, or because the ACL-ARC adapter is not adding much value and so the ad-

ditional values are leading to overfitting.

Finally, while the Cross Fusion results for SCIERC and CHEMPROT were close to expected, aligning producing similar results to the individual Pfeiffer Adapters, the results for ACL-ARC were surprising. Cross Adapter Fusion for RoBERTa performed almost on par with DAPT. This means the model gained significant information from adapter outside of its domain. This could be because of the large amount of training data for CHEMPROT and also because CHEMPROT’s Biomed domain has a 21% overlap with the CS domain [5]

4. Conclusions

Through our experiments with natural language, low-resource tasks that extend beyond the original training domains of RoBERTa, we were able to demonstrate the capabilities of adapters to perform at par with fine-tuning alternatives for transfer learning tasks. While needing less than 3% of the total trainable parameters as compared to fine-tuning, the adapters performance for the tasks matched full fine-tuning.

We also see that the benefits of pre-training across domain and tasks applied to adapters as well. Remarkably, adapters provided comparable or superior performance to TAPT, making them particularly valuable for low-resource settings with low budget or data availability for training. Additionally, through comparing the two popular adapter architectures – Pfeiffer and Housby, we find Housby performed slightly better when trained in our larger datasets, but the fact that Pfeiffer is more parameter-efficient and comparable to Housby in lower resource tasks makes it a competitive contestant. This is in line with expectations given Housby is naturally more adept for more complex tasks.

Adapter fusion shows promise as a method to improve results beyond a single adapter without significantly increasing the number of parameters, particularly when the domain or task of the adapters overlap.

Future work could explore additional adapter architectures, and their application across a wider range of NLP tasks and domains. We can also study the potential of Adapter Fusion to train on a completely new task.

5. Appendix

Appendix A. Team Members

Our team was made up of three members. We all participated in periodic zoom calls where we discussed the technical details and work allocation of the project with equal participation from all.

Student Name	Contributed Aspects	Details
Girish Sharma	Implementation and Analysis	Initial fine-tuning and adapter experiments with 5 seeds. Used manual hyper-parameter optimization. Comparison of Pfeiffer and Houlsby adapter architectures.
Matias Vizcaino	Implementation and Analysis	Using Optuna-based hyper-parameter optimization for fine-tuning and adapter experiments. Created final results for fine-tuning and adapters, studied the potential of adapters as an alternative to TAPT.
William Gleason	Implementation and Analysis	Study of adapter composition using Adapter Fusion and other techniques.

Table A.5. Contributions of team members.

Appendix B. Task Dataset Balance & Illustration of Predictions

Figure B.4. Class Distribution for task datasets

Figure B.5. True vs Predicted labels for SciERC task using RoBERTa base model (Houlsby Adapter)

Appendix C. HuggingFace Base Models Used

The list below shows the pre-trained models used for the three tasks.

Task	Model Type	Downloaded from
ACL-ARC	Base	roberta-base
	DAPT	allenai/cs_roberta_base
	TAPT	allenai/dsp_roberta_base_tapt_citation_intent_1688
	DAPT_TAPT	allenai/dsp_roberta_base_dapt_cs_tapt_citation_intent_1688
SciERC	Base	roberta-base
	DAPT	allenai/cs_roberta_base
	TAPT	allenai/dsp_roberta_base_tapt_sciie_3219
	DAPT_TAPT	allenai/dsp_roberta_base_dapt_cs_tapt_sciie_3219
CHEMPROT	Base	roberta-base
	DAPT	allenai/biomed_roberta_base
	TAPT	allenai/dsp_roberta_base_tapt_chemprot_4169
	DAPT_TAPT	allenai/dsp_roberta_base_dapt_biomed_tapt_chemprot_4169

Table C.6. Model Sources for Different Tasks

Appendix D. Adapters vs Full FineTuning

Dataset	Model	Fine-Tuning	Pfeiffer	Houlsby	Pfeiffer vs FT	Houlsby vs FT
ACL-ARC	RoBERTA Base	66.34	67.12	65.53	1.18%	-1.22%
	TAPT	69.49	67.22	65.12	-3.27%	-6.29%
	DAPT	74.65	73.32	74.03	-1.78%	-0.83%
	DAPT_TAPT	74.89	73.20	72.24	-2.26%	-3.54%
SCIERC	RoBERTA Base	80.02	81.60	81.32	1.97%	1.62%
	TAPT	80.95	80.80	80.92	-0.19%	-0.04%
	DAPT	83.08	82.48	82.55	-0.72%	-0.64%
	DAPT_TAPT	81.55	81.47	88.81	-0.10%	8.90%
CHEMPROT	RoBERTA Base	80.69	80.38	80.95	-0.38%	0.32%
	TAPT	79.88	80.80	80.67	1.15%	0.99%
	DAPT	81.72	81.85	82.16	0.16%	0.54%
	DAPT_TAPT	81.71	81.67	82.29	-0.05%	0.71%
Average		77.91	77.66	78.05	-0.33%	0.17%

Table D.7. Test accuracy for classification tasks across different pre-trained models. For each task and pre-trained model, the model with the best validation set accuracy is chosen. We report the mean test accuracy and s.e.m. across runs with different random seeds.

Appendix E. Training Environment and Hyper-Parameter Optimization

Table E.8. Fine-Tuning Hyperparameters

Hyperparameter	Value
Number of Training Epochs	10
Per-Device Training Batch Size	16
Per-Device Evaluation Batch Size	8
Learning Rate	2×10^{-5}
Dropout	0.1

Table E.9. Optuna Search Space

Parameter	Search Space
Learning Rate	Loguniform distribution between 1×10^{-5} and 1×10^{-3}
Batch Size	Discrete values: 16, 32, 64, 128
Number of Training Epochs	Uniform distribution between 5 and 15 (inclusive integers)

Table E.10. Best Hyperparameters for Adapter Training Across Different Tasks

Study	Adapter	Learning Rate	Batch Size	Epochs
ACL-ARC				
ROBERTA	Pfeiffer	0.000793	16	15
ROBERTA	Houlsby	0.000477	32	12
TAPT	Pfeiffer	0.000983	32	11
TAPT	Houlsby	0.000472	32	11
DAPT	Pfeiffer	0.000581	32	14
DAPT	Houlsby	0.000914	32	9
DAPT_TAPT	Pfeiffer	0.000332	16	14
DAPT_TAPT	Houlsby	0.000310	16	9
SCIERC				
SCIERC ROBERTA	Pfeiffer	0.000586	32	13
ROBERTA	Houlsby	0.000953	32	9
TAPT	Pfeiffer	0.000696	64	15
TAPT	Houlsby	0.000628	16	13
DAPT	Pfeiffer	0.000393	32	15
DAPT	Houlsby	0.000973	16	13
DAPT_TAPT	Pfeiffer	0.000870	64	14
DAPT_TAPT	Houlsby	0.000994	16	13
CHEMPROT				
ROBERTA	Pfeiffer	0.000224	16	12
ROBERTA	Houlsby	0.000588	16	11
TAPT	Pfeiffer	0.000365	32	7
TAPT	Houlsby	0.000346	16	9
DAPT	Pfeiffer	0.000224	16	8
DAPT	Houlsby	0.000396	16	5
DAPT_TAPT	Pfeiffer	0.000780	16	12
DAPT_TAPT	Houlsby	0.000857	16	9

Appendix F. Model layers

Layers shown with parameter counts. Only showing the 1st layer for sample purposes. RoBERTa has 11 repeating layers. Note the difference between the Pfeiffer and Houlsby Adapters. Pfeiffer configuration adds adapter modules only between feed-forward layers. Houlsby configuration adds adapters within the multi-head attention layers of each block, in addition to the feed-forward layers.

Table F.11. Description of Layers in Different Models

Layer Description	RoBERTa Model	Pfeiffer Adapter	Houlsby Adapter
Repeating Layers			
roberta.embeddings.LayerNorm.bias	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.self.query.weight	589824	589824	589824
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.self.query.bias	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.self.key.weight	589824	589824	589824
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.self.key.bias	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.self.value.weight	589824	589824	589824
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.self.value.bias	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.output.dense.weight	589824	589824	589824
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.output.dense.bias	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.output.LayerNorm.weight	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.attention.output.LayerNorm.bias	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.adapters.adapter_down.0.weight	-	-	36864
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.adapters.adapter_down.0.bias	-	-	48
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.adapters.adapter_up.weight	-	-	36864
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.adapters.adapter_up.bias	-	-	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.intermediate.dense.weight	2359296	2359296	2359296
roberta.encoder.layer.0.intermediate.dense.bias	3072	3072	3072
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.dense.weight	2359296	2359296	2359296
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.dense.bias	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.LayerNorm.weight	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.LayerNorm.bias	768	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.adapters.adapter_down.0.weight	-	36864	36864
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.adapters.adapter_down.0.bias	-	48	48
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.adapters.adapter_up.weight	-	36864	36864
roberta.encoder.layer.0.output.adapters.adapter_up.bias	-	768	768
roberta.encoder.layer.1.attention.self.query.weight	589824	589824	589824
Final Layers			
classifier.dense.weight	589824	-	-
classifier.dense.bias	768	-	-
classifier.out_proj.weight	4608	-	-
classifier.out_proj.bias	6	-	-
roberta.pooler.dense.weight	-	589824	589824
roberta.pooler.dense.bias	-	768	768
heads.default.0.weight	-	589824	589824
heads.default.0.bias	-	768	768
heads.default.2.weight	-	768	768
heads.default.2.bias	-	768	768
heads.default.3.bias	-	50265	50265
heads.base_citation_intent.1.weight	-	589824	589824
heads.base_citation_intent.1.bias	-	768	768
heads.base_citation_intent.4.weight	-	4608	4608
heads.base_citation_intent.4.bias	-	6	6

Appendix G. Source Code

Source code can be found at the following link: <https://github.gatech.edu/avizcaino3/CS-7643-EfficiencyLane.git>

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